

Transient Assisted Processing (TAP): An Optimized Balance of Sustainability, Precision, and Throughput for Advanced Processing

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The transition to three-dimensional device architectures and the integration of ultra-thin materials introduce significant patterning challenges, necessitating etching processes with Angstrom-level precision and control. Simultaneously, dry etching is the dominant contributor to emissions in wafer manufacturing, underscoring the urgent need for sustainable solutions. From both an economic and an environmental perspective, processes with high throughput and low consumption of harmful gases are highly desirable in the semiconductor industry. While Atomic Layer Etching (ALE) offers excellent controllability, its high gas consumption and low throughput make this approach suitable only where extreme precision is required and for layers ≤ 10 nm [1], but not all steps/ layers. An ideal etching approach would propose the precision of ALE with the throughput of conventional continuous plasma etching while keeping the consumption of harmful gases and energy low.

Recently, a novel paradigm—transient-assisted plasma (TAP) processing—has been introduced to address this challenge [2]. TAP is based on the transient of reactants and operates in the cycle, alternating between two key phases: the injection of reactant gas is sustained for a short time and then stopped, resulting in a gas transient that can be synchronized or not with plasma ignition, as illustrated in Figure 1. By strategically controlling the dosage and timing of reactive gases, TAP enhances process controllability, enabling the preservation of surface composition and minimizing undesirable interactions. Unlike conventional methods that rely on continuous gas injection, TAP employs short-pulse (≤ 1 s) reactant delivery, benefiting from outgassing phenomena to enhance reactant utilization. This approach significantly reduces overall gas consumption and reliance on environmentally hostile gases relative to both ALE and traditional Reactive Ion Etching (RIE) [3].

The versatility of TAP has been demonstrated by etching a large variety of materials, including metal alloys (binary such as NbTiN, ternary such as InGaZnO), dielectrics (SiO₂), and common sacrificial materials (resist descum, amorphous Carbon, Spin-on-Glass, TiN, amorphous Silicon, etc.) [3,4]. Beyond etching, TAP has also been successfully employed for in-situ hard-mask deposition and cleaning damage-sensitive materials, further highlighting its adaptability[5,6]. Fig 2 shows examples of TAP performance on pattern fidelity, scalability, controllability over etched depth and surface composition, gas consumption, and throughput. Its ability to accommodate a broad range of reactive and rare gases positions TAP as a scalable and highly flexible solution for next-generation semiconductor manufacturing.

Fig 1. Schematic diagram of the general TAP process

Fig 2. a) Cross-SEM Images showing pattern fidelity of TAP, b) linear etch depth as a function of number of cycles, c) Etch rate comparison among conventional etching, ALE, and TAP, d) XPS and EDX analysis demonstrating control over surface composition and sidewall residues, and e) Gas consumption comparison between ALE and TAP to etch 30 nm IGZO.

References

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